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THE ROLE OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND WORK ENGAGEMENT ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEADER-MEMBER EXCHANGE AND JOB SATISFACTION

LİDER-ÜYE ETKİLEŞİMİ VE İŞ TATMİNİ ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİDE ALGILANAN ÖRGÜTSEL DESTEK VE İŞE BAĞLILIĞIN ROLÜ

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Abstract: This research aims to comprehend the the mediating roles of perceived organizational support and work engagement in the effect of leader-member exchange on employees' job satisfaction. Namely, the main purpose is to contribute to this gap in the current knowledge. Structural equation modelling method (SEM) method has been used to analyse multiple variable complex models including direct and indirect relationships. Five-point Likert scale quantitative data was collected. Confirmatory factor analyses have been conducted to verify the convergent validity. Composite reliability has been used to testify reliability and AVE values indicated discriminant validity of the scales. The hypotheses have been tested by means of SEM. Consequently, it has been empirically proven that leader-member exchange has a positive impact on job satisfaction. Furthermore, both perceived organizational support and work engagement play mediating role in the relationship between leader-member exchange and job satisfaction. These findings are in accordance with the extant literature. This study attempts clarify the mechanism behind the relationship between leader-member exchange and job satisfaction by examining the role of perceived organizational support and work engagement concurrently.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Leader-Member Exchange, Work Engagement, Job Satisfaction

JEL: M12, M16

Öz: Bu araştırmada, algılanan örgütsel destek ve işe bağlılığın aracı rolleri aracılığıyla lider-üye etkileşiminin çalışanların iş tatmini üzerindeki doğrudan ve dolaylı etkilerinin incelenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Çalışma mevcut literatürdeki bu boşluğu kapatmayı amaçlamaktadır. Yapısal eşitlik modeli yöntemi, son derece çok değişkenli karmaşık modellerin analizinde kullanılır. Doğrudan ve dolaylı ilişkileri açıklamayı sağlar. Bu nedenlerden dolayı seçilmiştir. Yakınsama geçerliliği için doğrulayıcı faktör analizi uygulanmıştır. Ölçek güvenilirliği ise bileşik güvenilirlik katsayısı ile anlaşılmıştır. Ayrışma geçerliliği belirlenirken AVE değerleri kullanılmıştır. Hipotezler yapısal eşitlik modeli yöntemi kullanılarak test edilmiştir. Sonuç olarak lider-üye etkileşiminin iş tatmini üzerinde olumlu etkisi olduğu ampirik olarak kanıtlanmıştır. Ayrıca hem algılanan örgütsel destek hem de işe bağlılık, lider-üye etkileşimi ve iş tatmini arasındaki ilişkiye aracılık etmektedir. Bu sonuçlar mevcut literatür ile uyumludur. Bu çalışma, algılanan örgütsel destek ve işe bağlılığın eş

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zamanlı rolünü inceleyerek Lider-Üye Etkileşimi ve İş Tatmini arasındaki ilişkinin arkasındaki mekanizmayı anlamaya çalışmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Algılanan Örgütsel Destek, İşe Bağlılık, Lider-Üye Etkileşimi, İş Tatmini*

1. Introduction

Economic, technological, and demographic changes exert influence on employee job satisfaction in today's dynamic work environment (Aydogmus et al., 2018: 81). Job satisfaction reflects a person's positive emotional experiences because of their job appraisal (Locke, 1969: 1304). According to Rainey (2009: 298), "job satisfaction is prominent intensively studied concept in organizational research". Research indicates that job satisfaction is positively linked to organizational commitment (Kim and Brymer, 2011: 1025; Mwesigwa, Tusiime and Ssekiziyivu, 2020: 262; Bashir and Gani, 2020: 534), job performance (Chao et al., 2015: 1827; Tella and Ibinaiye, 2020: 44), and organizational performance (Vermeeren, Kuipers, and Steijn, 2014: 187). Several antecedent variables, including communication with supervisors (Blegen, 1993: 36), supervisory behaviors (Brown and Peterson, 1993: 68), and leadership (Cantarelli, Belardinelli, and Belle, 2016: 115) have been as major factors of job satisfaction.

Organizational leadership has impact on assisting individual and group efforts to achieve common goals (Yukl, 2012: 66). Therefore, leaders have crucial roles in the organizational setting and the perception of followers (Christian et al., 2011: 95). Apart from leadership styles, leader-member exchange (LMX) has significant deal of research interest due to its positive influence on task performance, contextual performance, and job satisfaction of the employees (Epitropaki et al., 2016: 1092). Leadership studies cover the domains of the leader, the follower, and leader-follower relationship. LMX theory is a relationship-based concept concentrating on leader-follower mutual relationship. According to the theory, effective leadership requires building a mature relationship among the leader and followers, thus resulting in desirable consequences for both individuals and organizations (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995: 225).

Although extant literature confirmed the significant effect of LMX on job satisfaction (Epitropaki et al., 2016: 1091), further research should be performed to clarify the mechanism behind this relationship. This research covers perceived organizational support and work engagement as potential mechanisms linking LMX to job satisfaction. Perceived organizational support (Wayne et al., 2002: 596) and work engagement (Lebron et al., 2018: 170; Aggarwal et al., 2020: 8) are key variables linked to LMX, but the concurrent mediating roles of these variables between LMX and job satisfaction have yet to be explored.

The main objective of this research is to extend the current literature regarding organizational behaviour. The contribution of the study is a better comprehension of the mechanisms underlying how work engagement and perceived organizational support mediate the relationship between leader-member exchange and job satisfaction. The literature indicates that a lot of academics in Western countries are curious about the LMX and work-related consequences' relationships (Lebron et al., 2018: 169); however, research on this topic in the Turkish context is scarce (Pellegrini and Scandura, 2006: 270; Erdogan, Liden, and Kraimer, 2006: 398). Furthermore, even though LMX theory is mostly studied in the management field, the relationship

between LMX and salespeople's job satisfaction has received little research interest (Li, Zhu, and Park, 2018: 1913). In the current study, it is assumed that LMX affects job satisfaction through influencing salespeople's perceptions of organizational support and work engagement.

2. Conceptual Background

This study is centered on the social exchange theory (SET) (Blau 1964). SET is an important theoretical approach for figuring out workplace behavior (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005: 874). It depends upon the concept that social exchange entails a series of interdependent relations resulting in a sense of obligation. According to SET, these interdependent interactions may cause high-quality relationships in specific circumstances (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005: 882). SET suggests that when people believe someone has done something useful for them, they will feel obligated to repay good faith action (Brown & Treviño, 2006: 607; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005: 882). In an organization, the social exchange process begins when a manager treats followers either positively or negatively. A follower then may choose to engage in good or bad behavior in exchange for this behavior. Thus, employees may have positive attitudes toward the organization when they observe desirable behaviors in the workplace, such as high organizational support and justice (Cropanzano et al., 2017: 479). In the theoretical model, it is assumed that high-quality LMX impacts perceived organizational support and subsequently work engagement increases job satisfaction. The model shown in Figure 1 was created after reviewing theoretical background.

Figure 1. Theoretical Model

2.1. Perceived Organizational Support

Eisenberger et al. (1986) proposed the concept of perceived organizational support (SPT) for the first time. SPT is defined as "employees' belief" about how much their contributions to the organization are valued (Eisenberger et al., 1986: 501). The social exchange theory is associated with organizational support theory. With regards to this theory, SPT satisfies employees' socioemotional needs; thus, employees have an internal commitment to reciprocate the support of the organization by displaying supportive work-related outcomes and assisting the organization in reaching the objectives (Eisenberger et al., 1986: 501; Kurtessis et al., 2017: 1855).

2.2. Work Engagement

Work engagement (WEG) has received increased scholarly attention since introduced by Kahn (1990). It is outlined as “a state of mind where a person working is completely absorbed in the task at hand, feeling energized and enthusiastic about it” (Bakker, 2017: 67). Kahn (1990) described work engagement as the eagerness of employees to commit their physical, cognitive, and emotional resources to organizational performance. The constructs of the concept are identified by Schaufeli et al. (2002: 74) as vigor, dedication, and absorption. In this study, these elements were combined to produce an overall measure of involvement.

2.3. Leader-Member Exchange

The social exchange theory, which emphasizes reciprocity, trust, and fairness between leaders and followers, served as the principal basis for the concept of LMX (Lebron et al., 2018: 160). According to LMX, a relationship-based leadership approach, effective leadership occurs when mature relationships are created between the leader and followers, leading to desirable outcomes (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995: 220). Leaders form several types of relationships with each follower rather than on the same level with all followers (Liden and Maslyn, 1998: 43). These relationships can vary from “high-quality exchanges” identified by strong mutual trust to “low-quality exchanges” identified as weak mutual trust and reliance solely on employment contracts. This relationship may evolve into a partnership based on mutual trust, respect, obligation, and accomplishment of common objectives, ensuring that the needs of both parties are addressed (Liden and Maslyn, 1998: 45; Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995: 227).

2.4. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction (JSF) is explained by Locke (1976: 1304) as “a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences”. For Spector (1997: 3), JSF is a prominent concept since it is an indicator of good treatment of employees and may have an influence on employee behaviors that affect organizational performance. Job satisfaction is critical for employees to be happy in an organization and to take ownership of their duties. Multidimensional instruments that include pay, promotions, coworkers, supervision, job conditions, fringe benefits, and nature of work have been used as well as unidimensional instruments (Spector, 1997: 5). In this research, the job satisfaction level of employees was investigated using a unidimensional job satisfaction model.

3. Hypothesis Development

3.1. Mediator Role of Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement

Job satisfaction is defined by Locke (1976: 1304) as “a pleasurable or positive emotional state”. Some research (Gerstner and Day, 1997: 838; Dulebohn et al., 2012: 1735) indicated that LMX had a significant and positive relationship with JSF. Along with the direct impact of LMX on JSF, it’s also predicted that WEG and SPT may have mediating effects on this relationship. First, as argued above, LMX positively effects WEG, and WEG positively effects JSF. The research in the literature displays that WEG mediates the relationship between LMX and outcomes (Breevaart et al.,

2015: 763; Lebron et al., 2018: 160; Aggarwal et al., 2020: 9). Second, LMX positively effects SPT, and SPT positively effects JSF. According to some studies SPT mediates the link between LMX and outcomes (Rokhim and Devina, 2019; Qureshi, Zaman, and Butt, 2020: 67). The following hypothesis is created considering the studies mentioned above.

H₁: Organizational Support and Work Engagement has mediator role in the relationship between Leader-Member Exchange and Job Satisfaction

3.2. Leader-Member Exchange and Perceived Organizational Support

The current study, as was already revealed, is centered in social exchange theory. SPT and LMX are two types of social exchanges that are examined in studies. SPT refers to interactions between an organization and its employees, whereas LMX refers to exchanges between a leader and subordinates. Therefore, SPT is positively related to high-quality LMX. The effectiveness of the relationship between the leader and followers is a crucial aspect of LMX, and SPT is concerned with employee-organization exchange relationships (Wayne et al., 2002: 83). The treatment of supervisors has a significant effect on employees because supervisors represent the organization. The followers are likely to interpret their manager's favorable or unfavorable treatment as an indication of organizational support (Rhodes and Eisenberger, 2002: 698). Various research shows the LMX and SPT relationships (Wayne et al. 1997: 101, 2002: 595; Masterson et al., 2000: 746; Bellou and Dimou, 2022: 697). Studies further reveal that LMX is positively linked to SPT (Kurtessis et al., 2017: 1862). The following hypothesis is created considering the studies mentioned above.

H₂: Leader-Member Exchange has a direct effect on perceived Organizational Support

3.3. Leader-Member Exchange and Work Engagement

The social exchange theory (SET) indicates the positive relationship between LMX and WEG. According to SET, obligations are formed because of a set of interchanges between leader and followers in a reciprocal interdependent relationship (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005: 82). Thus, subordinates feel obliged to compensate leaders with higher employee outcomes, including organizational commitment, organizational citizenship, and work engagement (Agarwal et al., 2012: 11). SET also suggests that followers are probably to attach importance the favors they have been given in the hopes of receiving additional benefits. Therefore, followers are more likely to be closely connected to their leaders and display positive job attitudes to continue this relationship (Bao and Ge, 2019: 378). Some research shows the relationship between LMX and WEG (Breevaart et al., 2015: 757; Bao et al. 2018: 412; Lebron et al., 2018: 163). The following hypothesis is created considering the studies mentioned above.

H₃: Leader-Member Exchange has a direct effect on Work Engagement.

3.4. Work Engagement and Job Satisfaction

WEG and JSF are two separate concepts, but they are positively related to one another (Cote, Lauzer, and Stinglhamber 2021: 270). WEG differs from JSF in that it combines dedication, vigor, and absorption, while JSF is often a more passive indicator of employee happiness. However, to Bakker (2011: 267), much more likely to be content with their jobs. According to research JSF and WEG are related (Lin et al., 2020: 671; Cote et al., 2021: 270; Ozturk et al. 2021). Furthermore, a systematic

review of the literature indicates that WEG is related to JSF (Bailey et al., 2015). Following hypothesis is created considering the studies mentioned above.

H₄: Work Engagement has a direct effect on Job Satisfaction

3.5. Perceived Organizational Support and Job Satisfaction

Desirable work-related employee outcomes, including organizational commitment and job satisfaction, are supposedly to be influenced by SPT. Also, SPT is thought to boost employee JSF by addressing socio - emotional needs, elevating performance-reward expectations, and offering support when necessary (Rhoades and Eisenberger 2002: 678). Various studies in existing literature demonstrate a relationship between SPT and JSF (Eisenberger et al., 1997: 818; Patrick and Laschinger, 2006: 19; Zumrah and Boyle, 2015: 245; Islam and Ahmed, 2018: 306). Moreover, three meta-analyses (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002: 710; Ahmed et al., 2015: 632; Kurtessis e al., 2017: 1872) indicate that SPT is positively related to JSF. The following hypothesis is created considering the studies mentioned above.

H₅: Organizational Support has a direct effect on Job Satisfaction.

3.6. Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement

Employees with high WEG are stimulated and effective at their jobs. They have faith in their ability to meet the requirement of the work. Therefore, organizations that have engaged workers may have better organizational performance (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004: 308; Bakker and Demerouti, 2008: 215). Followers can be leaded to engage in activities that facilitate organizational performance through SPT. Consistent with social exchange theory, followers who perceive strong organizational support are more inclined to contribute to accomplishment of strategic goals of the organization through displaying engagement in the workplace (Aldabbas, Pinnington, and Lahrech, 2021: 6501). Previous studies indicate a significant SPT and WEG relationship (Kinnunen, Feldt, and Makikangaz, 2008: 122; Lan et al., 2020: 7; Aldabbas et al., 2021: 6501). A meta-analysis by Ahmed et al. (2015: 632) noticed that SPT improves WEG. The following hypothesis is developed considering the preceding studies.

H₆: Perceived Organizational Support has a direct effect on Work Engagement

4. Research Methods

The research scales were derived from the literature. Data were gathered using a questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale. The structural equation modeling method was used to expose direct-indirect relationships between vastly complex multiple variables. Confirmatory factor analyses had first been conducted to evaluate convergent validity. Likewise, composite reliability and AVE values were computed to prove the scales' reliability and discriminant validity, respectively. The hypotheses were validated using structural equation modeling, a multivariate statistical technique (Meydan & Şeşen, 2011: 21). This technique is also practiced for verifying the direct and indirect effects of variables (Civelek, 2018: 6) and to reduce measurement errors (Byrne, 2010: 3). SPSS and AMOS statistics programs were exploited for all analyses. Three separate models are tested simultaneously in the structural equation modelling method to testify the role of the mediating variable in the dependent and independent variables' relationships. The goals of developing three models are to separate the expected effects of dependent, independent, and mediator variables. The first model measures the direct effect of the dependent and independent variables. The effects of the independent variable and the mediator variables are measured in the second model. The effects of all conceptual model variables are measured concurrently in the third model. The above approach considers good fit values in all models. The standardized values of the available path analysis coefficients deduced from the conceptual model in three different modes are contrasted. When the mediator variables are included in the model, the significant relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable is checked to see if it becomes insignificant (Civelek, 2018: 57).

4.1. Measures and Sampling

The constructs of the theoretical model were evaluated by using five-point Likert scales. To measure LMX, the scale suggested by Graen and Uhl-Bien (1995); to measure WEG, the scale suggested by Schaufeli, Bakker, and Salanova (2006); to measure SPT, the scale suggested by Eisenberger et al. (1986); to measure JSF, the scale suggested by Brayfield and Rothe (1951) and revised by Yoon and Thye (2002) were used. All scales were translated to Turkish. A total of 192 valid questionnaires were collected from 250 questionnaires distributed to medical representatives of the pharmaceutical industry in Turkey. The research sample consists of employees with 20% holding a high school degree, 65% undergraduate degree, 15% postgraduate degree; in terms of age 32% is between 18-29 years old, 37% is between 30-39 years old, 26% is between 40-49 years old, 5% is over 50 years old.

4.2. Construct Validity and Reliability

To prepare data for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used initially (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). After principal component analysis, 24 items were still present. CFA then was employed to determine convergent validity. The CFA fit indices values shown in Table 1 (i.e., $\chi^2/DF = 1.905$, CFI=0.964, IFI=0.964, RMSEA= 0.069) were deemed satisfactory (Civelek, 2018: 16). As given in Table 2, average extracted variance values were close to or greater than the 0.5 limit point (Byrne, 2010: 288). The outcomes demonstrate the constructs' convergence validity. The square roots of the AVE values for each variable were calculated to ascertain discriminant validity. The diagonals in Table 2 show the AVE values' square roots. The correlation values in the same column are all less than the square roots of

the AVE values. The findings show that the discriminant validity is established (Civelek, 2018: 42).

Table 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results

Variables	Items	Standardized Factor Loads	Unstandardized Factor Loads
Perceived Organizational Support (SPT)	SPT0714	0.772	1
	SPT0411	0.689	0.747
	SPT0613	0.846	0.947
	SPT0815	0.880	1.060
	SPT0209	0.879	1.181
	SPT0108	0.781	1.010
	SPT0310	0.835	1.105
Work Engagement (WEG)	SPT0512	0.743	0.762
	WEG0627	0.764	1
	WEG0324	0.773	0.749
	WEG0425	0.802	0.788
	WEG0526	0.954	1.025
Leader-Member Exchange (LMX)	WEG0122	0.797	0.904
	WEG0223	0.885	1.007
	INT0232	0.678	1
	INT0333	0.733	0.866
	INT0636	0.889	1.223
Job Satisfaction (JSF)	INT0535	0.783	1.398
	INT0737	0.857	1.346
	INT0434	0.938	1.440
Job Satisfaction (JSF)	JSF0138	0.822	1
	JSF0441	0.883	1.096
	JSF0239	0.808	1.043
	JSF0340	0.780	0.881

p<0.01 for all items

Calculations were made to determine the constructs' reliability. Table 2's composite reliability and Cronbach's values are above the threshold of 0.7 suggested by Fornell & Larcker (1981). Table 2 also includes the dimensions' descriptive statistics, average variance extracted values, and Pearson correlations between the dimensions. The correlation between each variable in the conceptual model is examined before testing the functions of the mediator variables. Significant relationship between all variables is a prerequisite for this analysis (Baron & Kenny, 1986). All variables in the conceptual model have meaningful relationships, as listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Construct Descriptives, Reliability and Correlation

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. Organizational Support	(.805)			
2. Work Engagement	.648*	(.831)		
3. Leader-Member Exchange	.682*	.530*	(.817)	
4. Job Satisfaction	.657*	.742*	.530*	(.824)
Composite reliability	.936	.931	.923	.894
Average variance ext.	.649	.692	.669	.679
Cronbach α	.937	.930	.919	.915

*p < 0.05

Note: Values in diagonals are the square root of AVEs

5. Test of the Hypotheses

The confirmatory method known as covariance-based structural equation modeling (CB-SEM) was employed to test the hypotheses (Civelek, 2018: 26). Based on the goodness of fit indices, the structural model's fit was assessed (Civelek, 2018: 16). The three models which are utilized to test mediator roles, respectively, are found in Figure 2, 3 and 4. Figure 2 presents the path analysis results of Model 1. The outcomes of Model 1's path analysis are shown in Figure 2. Model 1 measured the direct relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The relationship is significant and positive. The model's fit indices fall within the accepted threshold. The model's fit indices were found to have the following values: $\chi^2/DF = 2.329$, CFI = 0.979, IFI = 0.979, RMSEA = 0.083.

Note: $\chi^2/DF = 2.329$, CFI = 0.979, IFI = 0.979, RMSEA= 0.083

Figure 2. Results of the Model 1

Note: $\chi^2/DF = 2.371$, CFI = 0.943, IFI = 0.944, RMSEA = 0.085

Figure 3. Results of the Model 2

The outcomes of Model 2's path analysis are shown in Figure 3. Direct connections between the independent variable and the mediator variables were quantified in the model. Relationships are meaningful and positive. The model's fit indices fall within the acceptable threshold. The following values were noticed: $\chi^2/DF = 2.371$, CFI = 0.943, IFI = 0.944, RMSEA = 0.085.

The outcomes of Model 3's path analysis are shown in Figure 4. The conceptual framework of the study was evaluated in Model 3. The model's fit indices fall within the acceptable threshold. The fit indices indicate the following values: $\chi^2/DF = 1.933$, CFI = 0.962, IFI = 0.963, RMSEA = 0.070.

Note: $\chi^2/DF = 1.933$, CFI = 0.962, IFI = 0.963, RMSEA = 0.070

Figure 4. Results of the Model 3

Table 3 provides an overview of the test outcomes for the conceptual model's hypotheses in each of the three models. H₁ hypothesis is supported because the relationship turned insignificant after involvement of mediators. This means that SPT and WEG has mediator role in the relationship between LMX and JSF.

Table 3. Hypotheses Test Results

Relationships		Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
LMX → JSF	(H ₁)	0.555*		0.012
LMX → SPT	(H ₂)		0.730*	0.734*
LMX → WEG	(H ₃)		0.160*	0.551*
WEG → JSF	(H ₄)			0.645*
SPT → JSF	(H ₅)			0.220*
SPT → WEG	(H ₆)		0.559*	
Model Fit Indices		$\chi^2/df=2.329$, CFI=0.979, IFI=0.979, RMSEA=0.083	$\chi^2/df=2.371$, CFI=0.943, IFI=0.944, RMSEA=0.085	$\chi^2/df=1.933$, CFI=0.962, IFI=0.963, RMSEA=0.070

Note: Path analysis coefficients are standardized.

*p<0.01

H₂ hypothesis is supported. This means LMX has a direct effect on SPT. H₃ hypothesis is supported. This means LMX has a direct effect on WEG. H₄ hypothesis is supported. This demonstrates that WEG has a direct effect on JSF. H₅ hypothesis is

supported. This indicates that SPT has a direct effect on JSF. H_6 hypothesis is supported. This indicates that SPT has a direct effect on WEG.

6. Conclusion & Discussion

The present study examined whether LMX influences job satisfaction and whether the relationship between LMX and job satisfaction is mediated by perceived organizational support and work engagement. Our survey of a sample of Turkish pharmaceutical industry representatives revealed that LMX significantly and positively effects job satisfaction. Furthermore, there are positive relationships between LMX and perceived organizational support, LMX and work engagement, perceived organizational support and job satisfaction, work engagement and job satisfaction. The results also indicate that LMX has an indirect effect on job satisfaction through perceived organizational support and work engagement. Thus, these findings support all the hypotheses in this study.

The literature's research demonstrates that LMX is related with both WEG and SPT. WEG mediates the connection between LMX and JSF (Breevaart et al., 2015: 763; Lebron et al., 2018: 171; Aggarwal et al., 2020: 9). LMX has a favorable impact on SPT, and SPT has a positive impact on JSF. Some research claim that SPT mediates the relationship between LMX and JSF (Rokhim and Devina 2019; Qureshi, Zaman, and Butt 2020: 67). This research is in line with the aforementioned studies because H_1 hypothesis is supported. According to the extant literature, SPT and LMX have a positive relationship. Several studies demonstrate correlations between LMX and SPT (Wayne et al. 1997:101, 2002: 595; Masterson et al., 2000: 746; Bellou and Dimou, 2022:697). Studies also demonstrate that LMX and SPT have a relationship (Kurtessis et al., 2017: 1862). H_2 is supported. Therefore, the finding of this study is coherent with the past research. The social exchange theory suggests that LMX and WEG have a relationship. Various studies demonstrate the connection between LMX and WEG (Breevaart et al., 2015: 757; Bao et al. 2018: 412; Lebron et al., 2018: 171). H_3 is supported. The results are incompatible with the above mentioned literature. WEG and JSF have a constructive relationship with one another (Cote, Lauzer, and Stinglhamber 2021: 270). JSF and WEG are related (Lin et al., 2020: 671; Cote et al., 2021: 270; Ozturk et al. 2021). Also, a thorough study of the literature reveals a connection between WEG and JSF (Bailey et al., 2015). H_4 is supported therefore this result is congruent to the aforementioned findings. Several research in the past literature reveal a relationship between SPT and JSF (Eisenberger et al., 1997: 818; Patrick and Laschinger, 2006: 19; Zumrah and Boyle, 2015:245; Islam and Ahmed, 2018: 306). Furthermore, according to some analyses, SPT is positively correlated with JSF (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002: 710; Ahmed et al., 2015: 632; Kurtessis et al., 2017: 1872). H_5 is supported therefore this result is line with above findings. Earlier research has found a significant link between SPT and WEG (Kinnunen, Feldt, and Makikangaz, 2008: 122; Lan et al., 2020: 7; Aldabbas et al., 2021: 6501). Some research discovered that SPT increases WEG (Ahmed et al., 2015: 632). As H_6 is supported, this conclusion is consistent with the earlier findings.

The leader is the prominent factor affecting the culture, structure, and climate in the organization. In this context, it is crucial to understand the mechanism that reveals the impact of LMX on employee job satisfaction. In this research, the mechanism that enables the conversion of LMX to job satisfaction is better understood. The function of SPT and WEG in this relationship is very crucial. This study has shown that employee satisfaction will not increase simply by improving LMX. The roles of SPT

and WEG cannot be neglected. Without SPT and WEG, LMX will not create JFS. In this context, it is very necessary for managers to carry out activities that support the employees in the organization. Because supporting activities enable the emergence of the WEG. The absence of one of the rings in this chain will prevent the occurrence of JSF. For this reason, leaders should not only be relationship-oriented, but also adopt organizational values to their employees. Behaviors that show that they care about them is the mechanism that creates JSF. Conducting future studies on different samples would be useful in terms of understanding whether these findings are also valid for employees working at various industries.

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